

**PREFERENCES FOR MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES:
A COMPARISON OF STUDENT AND TEACHER PERSPECTIVE
IN JAPANESE AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (JFL)
CLASSROOM IN SRI LANKA**

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Abstract:

This study was aimed to investigate the teachers' and students' preference of motivational strategies employed in motivating students to learn Japanese language in General Certificate of Education (G.C.E.) Advanced Level classes in Sri Lanka. The sample consisted of 27 Japanese as a Foreign Language (JFL) teachers and 275 students. An adapted questionnaire with 28 items was used to measure the perception of students' and teachers' towards using motivational strategies in JFL classroom. Fourteen items in the questionnaire targeted at measuring traditional strategies while the rest of the items measured innovative strategies. Descriptive statistics was used to find out the mean values of both the teachers' and students' preference of strategies and to prepare two lists of motivational strategies according to the priority order of rankings rated by teachers and students. The independent samples T-test was applied to determine the significant level of difference between the two groups. The results indicated that both students and teachers agree on the use of motivational strategies to motivate students. Nevertheless, it is statistically evident that students prefer innovative strategies than traditional strategies while teachers prefer both types of strategies equally. The findings revealed that there is a significant difference between these two motivational strategies as perceived by teachers and students.

Keywords: motivational strategies, foreign language learning, JFL teachers, innovative strategies, General Certificate of Education (G.C.E.) Advanced Level

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1. Introduction

In the process of learning a foreign/second language (L2), *“the learners’ enthusiasm, commitment and persistence are key determinants of success or failure”* (Dörnyei, 2001, p. 5). Motivation is an important factor in language learning and it is generally believed that the motivated students are more likely to achieve the learning targets than the others who are not (Sumiyoshi & Svetanant, 2017). It is a significant factor which influences students’ success or failure in learning a second/foreign language (Kondal, 2015; Kaboody, 2013; Cheng & Dörnyei, 2007). As identified by many theorists motivation is a multifaceted construct and also it includes attitudinal component which can be considered as a strong predictor towards learning languages since the attitudes influence on students’ behavior toward language achievement (Gardner, 1985). Further, students’ perceptions are also accepted as one of the key factors which have been studied by many researchers. It is defined as the process by which one receives and interprets information from the environment and it reflects someone’s emotions, feelings, needs, expectations etc. (Jahedizadeh et. al, 2016).

Learning a foreign language is a difficult task than learning other subjects in school educational programs. Learning a language is not a simple and easy process which cannot be accomplished simply by retaining the words or rules of its language. The strategies used by the teachers can be considered as an imperative determinant of motivating students towards learning a language. For the most part, the instructors investigate the way in which manner can advance learners’ engagement and their dynamic cooperation in classroom exercises so as to enhance the nature of learning (Guilloteaux, 2007). Indeed L2 learners with sufficient motivation achieve their target regardless of their language aptitude or other individual characteristics (Dörnyei, 2001). Therefore, motivating students is the pedagogical implication of motivation and is a teachers’ responsibility in order to improve or maintain the students’ level of motivation. Dörnyei (2001) suggests a number of strategies for motivating language learners. Though, he states that effectiveness of these motivational strategies should be confirmed by experimental research in various contexts before applying them in language classroom.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine the JFL teachers’ preference of motivational strategies employed to encourage and motivate the learning of Japanese language in the students at the G.C.E Advanced Level classes in Sri Lanka. Further, there was an attempt to determine whether there are any differences between teachers’ and students’ preference for motivational strategies which should be used to motivate students. Role of the teacher is one of the main sources that maintain students’ motivation for learning a language (Kakar & Pathan, 2017). The term motivation is generally used in both educational and research contexts. Motivational strategies refer to *“instructional interventions applied by the teacher to elicit and stimulate student motivation”* (Guilloteaux & Dörnyei, 2008, p.57). Lack of motivation is a major issue in language classes. Indeed, one of the main challenges of any foreign language teachers worldwide is motivating their learners. Hence, strategies used for motivating a language learner

should be believed as a significant aspect in L2 research (Cheng & Dörnyei, 2007) and it has been known as an important area of L2 motivational research. Although, empirical studies on how to motivate a language learner was a neglected area until 1990s and new attempt was focused towards implementing a more practical and education centered research on motivation which can be investigated regarding the teachers' perception on classroom practices and most relevant approaches used in the classroom (Dörnyei & Csizér, 1998). To fulfill this requirement number of studies have investigated the motivational strategies which can be applied to motivate the language learners and plenty of studies have adapted Dörnyei's motivational strategies framework (2001).

Most of these studies concluded that the teachers who were applied motivational strategies in language class have simply motivated their students. Further, it has been proven that learners' motivation is positively related to their achievement (Cho & Teo, 2013; Bernaus & Gardner, 2008; Bernaus, Wilson & Gardner, 2009). However, it is important to investigate the perception of both students and teachers, since most of the studies have been concentrated only on teachers' perception of using strategies or relationship between motivational strategies and student motivation. Nevertheless, a few studies have been focused on student perception too. Based on findings of previous studies, various strategies, which can be used to motivate learners and maintain their motivation, have been identified by continuous research based on language motivation. Although still there is a need to identify the perception of students and teachers about the importance of using them in various contexts. There were only few researches conducted in Sri Lanka related to motivation and language learning and this kind of research has not been given much attention during past years.

Therefore this study attempts to fulfill this gap in order to facilitate foreign language teachers to make better understanding regarding which strategies should be applied to improve and maintain students' motivation from both students' and teachers' perspective. Present study investigates the strategies preferred by JFL teachers and students in G.C.E Advanced Level classes in Sri Lanka. Further, it examines whether there is any difference between their preferences of motivational strategies. Further two lists of motivational strategies are prepared according to the priority order of rankings by teachers and students.

2. Literature Review

The role of teacher has been recognized as the most influential factor when motivating a learner in Previous studies (Dörnyei, 1994; Cheng & Dörnyei, 2007; Dörnyei, 2001; Dörnyei & Csizer, 1998). These studies have concluded that language teacher promotes learners' engagement and persistence in language learning process. Teacher plays *"multi-dimensional role; such as an initiator, facilitator, motivator, ideal model of target language speaker, mentor, consultant and mental supporter"* (Matsumoto, 2009, p.2). Dörnyei and Csizer (1998) argue based on the findings of their study of 200 Hungarian teachers, that teachers' behavior is the most influential tool of motivation in language classroom. Further, they claim that teachers' behavior and the techniques they use in the classroom

can influence the students' engagement in class. Therefore, without an argument the teacher can enhance students' motivation by applying various strategies to motivate them. Without sufficient motivation student cannot be able to achieve the long term goal even with extraordinary abilities, proper curriculum and good teaching (Guillteaux & Dörnyei, 2008).

Number of empirical studies has been conducted in this regard to identify the relationship between motivational strategies, students' motivation and achievement (Dörnyei & Csizer, 1998; Cheng & Dörnyei, 2007; Bernaus & Gardner, 2008). The findings of these studies have proved that motivated students are better in achievement. Further, these findings revealed the relationship between the strategies, motivation and achievement. During the recent decades, a large number of studies have been conducted to investigate the importance of students' motivation in second/ foreign language learning and it has been recognized as one of the most important key factor which determines the level of success or the failure in language learning (Bernaus & Gardner, 2008; Cheng and Dörnyei, 2007; Dörnyei, 1998).

Language motivation researches began since 1959 by the pioneering work of Wallace Lambert and Robert C. Gardner in Canada and Gardner established 'Socio-educational model' (Gardner & MacIntyre, 1993; Dörnyei, 2001). Their argument was that the learners' integrative motivation is influenced on the success or failure in language learning (Gardner, 2001). Further, they argued that many other factors can be depended on motivation as it is the main facet which influence on language learning. The 'socio educational model' is mainly focused on integrativeness and attitudes toward learning situations which demonstrate under the category of individual differences of learners. These two variables directly affect on students' motivation. Since more than four decades of research in language motivation, Lambert and Gardner's psychological approach was mostly supported to demonstrate the perspectives and aspects of learners' motivation (Guilloteaux, 2007). The motivation of the learners, explicate that 'the feelings of the learner regarding the target language, its' cultural values and their intrinsic or extrinsic reasons to learn the language'.

Generating students' motivation and positive attitudes towards the target language is most probably teachers' responsibility and it can be achieved by introducing various strategies. Motivational strategies are known as the techniques which encourage student and promote student behavior in language class which can be done by different ways (Dörnyei, 2001). Also, it is needed to maintain and protect the students' motivation as well as generating and initiating the motivation (Al Kaboody, 2013). Dörnyei (2001) presented the set of four principals which can promote students' motivation namely creating the basic motivational strategies, generating student motivation, maintaining and protecting motivation and encouraging positive self-evaluation (p.119). The list of motivational strategies grouped in to three dimensions known as the Language Level, the Learner Level and the Learning Situation Level in his framework of L2 motivation.

Most of researches have focused on examine the motives and analyzing the theories related to motivation than identifying the strategies which can be used to

develop student motivation. However, in this regard some studies were conducted to examine how teachers role influence students' motivation while the other studies have been focused on strategies used in the language classroom. Dörnyei and Csizer (1998) conducted empirical study and suggested 10 commandments of motivational strategies which can be supported to motivate students. The data was collected from 200 Hungarian teachers of English. They were asked their perception about the use of 51 strategies and how frequently they use them in the class. Based on the results, 10 motivational macro strategies were suggested. Later Dörnyei (2001) presented 102 motivational strategies which categorized in to four phases.

Cheng & Dörnyei (2007) conducted a large scale empirical survey which was the modified replication of Dörnyei and Csizer (1998) study. They followed the similar method applied by Dörnyei and Csizer in 1998, to explore the motivational strategies employed by English teachers in Taiwan. The results concluded that there were similarities and dissimilarities between the findings in Taiwan and Hungaria. Further, a large scale research investigates by Guilloteaux and Dörnyei (2008) in 40 ESOL classrooms in South Korea, with 1300 students and 27 teachers. A classroom observation instrument was used to assess the teachers' use of strategy in the classroom and a self-report questionnaire was used to measure students' motivation. It was examined relationship between teachers motivational strategy use and student motivation to learn a language. The language class was the unit of analysis. Based on the results they suggested that teachers' motivational strategies is related to students' motivated learning behavior.

Guilloteaux (2013) conducted a study with 268 EFL teachers in South Korea to evaluate the list of same motivational strategies used by Cheng & Dörnyei in 2007. Finding of this study revealed that teachers give less priority to motivate students and rarely use motivational strategies to 'generating a positive classroom climate' and 'adaptive group dynamics'. Further, it reports that teachers should give positive feedback and introduce more attractive learning task in order to motivate students.

Furthermore, a study has been conducted to investigate the language teaching strategies as reported by both teachers and students and the relationship between these strategies, students' motivation and English achievement by Bernaus and Gardner in 2008. The teachers and students responded to the list of 26 motivational strategies. The finding indicated that the both groups agreed on frequency of using some strategies only. Even though the motivational strategies reported by teachers were not related to motivation and achievement and the student perception on use of strategies was related with motivation.

Further, based on the findings, researchers suggest that generally teachers apply any strategy which they believe that may important to student. However, from the students' side they may not recognize the effort of teachers' use of strategies because their low interest in subject. Therefore, the researchers recommend that the teacher should be aware of students' perception too on using strategies before applying the strategies. In fact, in many language classrooms teacher should cover the prescheduled syllabus and some goal of the language course. Though, many research findings prove

that there is difference between the goal of the course and students' actual requirements. Hence, students complain is that they do not aware why they are given instructions by the teachers to participate for particular activities in the classroom. Therefore, it is teachers' responsibility to understand this situation to help students to achieve their goal.

Thus, as mentioned by Dörnyei (2001), students' perception regarding the teachers' use of motivational strategies is influenced on the effectiveness of teaching strategies in motivating learners. This issue is considered in the present study as emphasized by Bernaus and Gardner (2008). As highlighted in previous studies regarding the importance of this type of research, the present study intends to investigate both JFL students' and teachers' perceptions to examine the strategies which should be most appropriate and effective to Sri Lankan context from both groups of perspectives.

2.1 Research Questions

1. What motivational strategies used in the classroom do JFL teachers think most effective?
2. What motivational strategies used in the classroom do JFL students find most effective?
3. Is there any significant difference between the motivational strategies preferred by JFL teachers and students?

3. Methodology

The following steps were undertaken in order to select the sample, preparing the survey instrument, data collection and to analyze the data.

3.1 Participants

The participants for this study consisted of 27 JFL teachers and their 275 students in G.C.E Advanced Level classes in Sri Lanka. The students were in grade 13, the last year of secondary school. Out of the nine provinces, only six provinces were selected for the study since currently Japanese language studies are being taught only in these provinces. Probability sampling method was used to select the sample. The sample consisted of 54% from the western province, 15.6% from the North Western, 12.9% from Sabaragamuwa, 11.3% from Southern, 3.6% from North Central and 2.6 % from Central province.

3.2 Instrument

The instrument consisted of a list of 28 motivational strategies with a five point Likert scale, which included 14 traditional strategies and 14 innovative strategies. The original questionnaire was constructed in English. It was translated into Sinhala and reviewed by two experts for ensuring the validity of the instrument.

The list of motivational strategies were adapted from Bernaus and Gardner (2008) and Dörnyei and Cheng (2007). The teachers and students were asked to rate their level of agreement on using motivational strategies to motivate students, ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”. Bernaus and Gardner’s (2008) strategy list is consisted 26 items. One item was deleted since it was not applicable in Sri Lankan context. Additionally, three items were adapted from Dörnyei and Cheng (2007) list of motivational strategies to make equal items for innovative and traditional strategies. The pilot study was carried out with 30 students and 20 teachers in Advanced Level classes. Chronbach alpha was 0.963 and 0.893 for innovative strategies and 0.935 and 0.809 traditional strategies for students and teachers respectively.

3.3 Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered among the students and teachers after seeking permission from the principle of the each school. All participants were briefly informed the objectives of the study before the survey started.

3.4 Data Analysis

The SPSS (Version 21) program was used to analyze the data. In order to examine the perception of teachers and students on using motivational strategies in the class, descriptive statistics was applied to calculate the mean and standard deviation of the respondent. To determine the statistical significant difference of the level of agreement on motivational strategies perceived by teachers and students, Independent Sample T-test was performed.

4. Results

In the following sections, the strategies preferred by students and teachers and the comparison of perceptions between the two groups are discussed. First, the students’ preferences of motivational strategies were ranked based on the mean values followed by teachers’ preferences. Further, the preference list was grouped in to three categories according to the level of agreement. The preferences of both groups are discussed below.

4.1 Motivational strategies preferred by JFL students

In order to find out the students’ preference of motivational strategies used by their teachers, the mean score and standard deviation of each innovative and traditional motivational strategy were calculated and ranked based on the criteria for mean value given by Cho and Teo (2013). The findings are presented in the following Table 1.

Table 1 : Students' agreement level on use of motivational strategies

Item No	Strategy Type	Mean	SD	Level of Agreement
12	I	4.7309	.58599	Strongly Agree
28	I	4.6109	.69767	Strongly Agree
27	I	4.5636	.73900	Strongly Agree
4	I	4.5491	.76913	Strongly Agree
21	I	4.5455	.70499	Strongly Agree
2	T	4.5127	.78001	Strongly Agree
3	T	4.5055	.72177	Strongly Agree
22	I	4.5018	.77070	Strongly Agree
9	I	4.4909	.73675	Strongly Agree
6	T	4.4764	.74627	Strongly Agree
13	T	4.4545	.72540	Strongly Agree
5	T	4.4473	.86283	Strongly Agree
15	T	4.4364	.79606	Strongly Agree
14	I	4.4364	.83630	Strongly Agree
20	I	4.4291	.72335	Strongly Agree
17	I	4.4218	.79015	Strongly Agree
19	T	4.4000	.77836	Strongly Agree
1	I	4.4000	.76892	Strongly Agree
26	I	4.3891	.80909	Strongly Agree
23	T	4.3855	.76688	Strongly Agree
7	T	4.3709	.81984	Strongly Agree
25	I	4.2945	.81756	Strongly Agree
8	T	4.2909	.91366	Strongly Agree
10	T	4.2000	.87546	Agree
11	T	4.1964	.89483	Agree
24	I	4.1927	.90575	Agree
16	T	4.0873	.93181	Agree
18	T	3.2036	1.04392	Neutral

*I= Innovative Strategies **T= Traditional Strategies

Table 1 presents the motivational strategies perceived by JFL students in Advanced level class. It clearly shows that students strongly agree with the 23 strategies which may increase their motivation to learn Japanese. Most agreed strategy of students' preference list is item no 12, "I like it when my Japanese teacher makes us aware about the Japanese culture" ($\bar{x} = 4.7309$). The item no 18, "I like it when my Japanese teacher allows us to speak Sinhala in class" was given the least agreement among the strategies list. It means that students do not consider this strategy much important when compared with other strategies. Interestingly, students prefer innovative strategies as the first five strategies in their preference list. Further, it shows that students strongly agree with the use of 23 motivational strategies out of 28, for motivating them to learn Japanese which rated as 'strongly agree'. Table 2 shows the mean values of students' agreement of using innovative and traditional motivational strategies.

Table 2: The mean values of students' preference of innovative and traditional motivational strategies

Type of Strategy	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Innovative	275	1.36	8.57	4.4821	.58269
Traditional	275	1.79	5.00	4.2834	.52270

Table 2 shows that the mean value for the Innovative strategies ($\bar{x} = 4.4821$) is slightly higher than the traditional strategies ($\bar{x} = 4.2834$). It means that students prefer the use of innovative strategies rather than traditional strategies. However, mean values for both strategies are within the range of "Strongly Agree" according to the criteria referred for this study ($\bar{x} = 4.21 - 5.00$).

3.7 Motivational strategies preferred by JFL teachers

The motivational strategies preferred by teachers are discussed here. In order to find out the mean score and standard deviation for the teachers' preference of the motivational strategies, descriptive statistics was used. The findings are given in the Table 3.

Table 3: Teachers' agreement level on use of motivational strategies

Item No	Strategy Type	Mean	SD	Level of Agreement
27	I	4.4444	.57735	Strongly agree
12	I	4.4444	.64051	Strongly agree
8	T	4.4444	.57735	Strongly agree
1	I	4.3333	.73380	Strongly agree
19	T	4.2963	.72403	Strongly agree
3	T	4.2963	.60858	Strongly agree
9	I	4.2963	.66880	Strongly agree
23	T	4.2593	.59437	Strongly agree
26	I	4.2593	.65590	Strongly agree
10	T	4.2593	.59437	Strongly agree
21	I	4.1852	.83376	Agree
2	T	4.1481	.76980	Agree
28	I	4.1481	.76980	Agree
17	I	4.0370	.64935	Agree
4	I	4.0370	.70610	Agree
20	I	4.0370	.70610	Agree
16	T	4.0000	.67937	Agree
14	I	4.0000	.87706	Agree
11	T	3.9630	.64935	Agree
13	T	3.9259	.82862	Agree
5	T	3.8889	.64051	Agree
15	T	3.8519	.94883	Agree
7	T	3.4815	.75296	Agree
22	I	3.4815	.80242	Agree
6	T	3.4815	.75296	Agree
18	T	3.2593	.71213	Neutral
25	I	3.0741	.91676	Neutral
24	I	3.0000	.87706	Neutral

Table 3 shows the teachers level of agreement on using the 28 motivational strategies for motivating JFL students. Teacher's average agreement level for the motivational strategies is 3.9762 which in the range of "agree". Generally, teachers agree on using motivational strategies in the class. Item no 27 "I recognize my students' effort and compliment their success" ($\bar{x} = 4.4444$) were selected by all teachers as the most effective strategy which should be used in the classroom to motivate their students. The lowest mean value among the 28 strategies is item no 24, "I give questionnaires to my students to evaluate my teaching at the end of the semester" ($\bar{x} = 3.0$). Ten strategies out of 28 motivational strategies are rated as "strongly agree" and fifteen items are rated as "agree". Table 4 shows the mean values of teachers' preference of innovative and traditional motivational strategies.

Table 4: The mean values of students' preference of innovative and traditional motivational strategies

Type of Strategy	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Innovative	27	3.00	4.71	3.9841	.47765
Traditional	27	3.14	4.50	3.9683	.31282

The mean values are 3.9841 and 3.9683 for both types of strategies. There is no significant difference between mean values which shows that JFL teachers almost agree to use both innovative and traditional strategies for motivating students.

3.8 Differences between teachers' preference of motivational strategies and students' preference

In order to analyze the differences between teachers' and students' preference of motivational strategies, the Independent sample t-test was employed. The result shows in the Table 5.

Table 5: The results of independent sample t-test

Student Mean	SD	Teachers Mean	SD	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
8.7522	1.01029	7.9524	.7530	4.003	300	.000	.79983	.19979

The result of t-test reveals a significant difference between the teachers' average preference of motivational strategies and the students' average preference at the 0.01 level ($p < .01$). Table 5 shows the difference between the teachers' preference and the students' preference for each of the 28 motivational strategies. The mean value for the students is 8.7522 ± 1.01029 and the mean value for the teachers was $7.9524 \pm .75307$. The P-value in the test is less than 0.001. Hence, there is a statistically significant difference between the motivational strategies perceived by teachers and students. The top five ranking of both teachers' and students' preference for motivational strategies are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Top five rankings of motivational strategies

Item no	Statement- Student	Item No	Statement- Teacher
12	I like it when my Japanese teacher makes us aware about the Japanese culture	27	I recognize my students' effort and compliment their success
28	I like it when my Japanese teacher creates a pleasant and relaxed atmosphere in the class	12	I make the students aware about the Japanese culture.
27	I like it when my Japanese teacher recognizes my effort and compliments my success	8	I address questions to the whole class.
4	I like it when my Japanese teacher makes us play games in class	1	I make my students practice dialogues in pair
21	I like it when my Japanese teacher supplements our textbook with other materials	19	I lay down rules and regulations to be followed in class (e.g. Hand in homework on time, Be honest, etc.)

4. Conclusion

This comparative study investigated the JFL teachers' and students' preference of motivational strategies employed to motivate students' learning of Japanese Language in G.C.E Advanced Level class in Sri Lanka. To this aim, the survey method was used to collect the data under the quantitative research approach. The study results show that both teachers and students agree to the use of motivational strategies in the classroom generally in order to motivate students. Although students prefer innovative strategies than traditional strategies and teachers prefer both strategies equally. This result is supported by the findings of the study conducted by Cho & Teo (2013). Interestingly, the ranking order of the agreement level for motivational strategies is different between the teachers and students. It means that teachers' perception about which strategies should be used in the class is different with students' perception about the strategies which they expect from teachers to apply in the classroom to motivate them. However, both groups have included the item 12 'Make the students aware about the Japanese culture' and item 27 'Recognize students' effort and compliment their success' in top five ranking which emphasizes that both teachers and students strongly agree on using these two strategies which support to motivate students. Further, significant difference found between the motivational strategies perceived by teachers and students. It concludes that strategies are differently perceived by JFL teachers and students in G.C.E. Advanced Level classes in Sri Lanka. The results suggest that teachers must be aware of the student preference of motivational strategies since it is useful when teachers use the most effective strategies in the classroom.

The findings show that students are interested to learn more about the Japanese culture. Therefore, teachers should apply the culture related activities as expected by students. It will make a more enjoyable learning environment which motivates the students. Further, all students agree that they like it when their Japanese teacher creates

a pleasant and relaxed atmosphere in the class. Teachers should plan how to make pleasant learning environment by using various strategies. Further both teachers and students agree that teacher should recognize students' effort and must appreciate when it is necessary. This will be encouraging students to work hard and achieve their goals. Therefore, teachers should be made aware in teacher training programmes about how to apply strategies effectively to motivate students.

As pointed out in a number of researches (Bernaus, Wilson & Gardner, 2009; Bernaus & Gardner, 2008) one of the main limitation of this study is that the actual use of motivational strategy was not examined directly as investigated in a few previous studies (e.g. Guilloteaux & Dörnyei, 2008). This study was mainly focused on students' and teachers' perception about using strategies. Cho & Teo (2013) state that examining students' perception on motivational strategy used by their teachers, is important to understand the realistic of the learning situation and it will support to compare the perception on strategies of both groups. Further, it is suggested that the teacher should be aware of students' preference of strategies and encourage using the most suitable strategies which can effectively improve students' motivation.

As mentioned in previous studies, generating students' motivation and supporting them to maintain positive attitudes towards target language is teachers' responsibility. Teacher can achieve this target by implementing different motivational strategies which increase the students' motivation. Teachers should know how to attract the students' attention to learn the language and increase their intrinsic and instrumental motivation. This can be done by identifying students' actual requirements and ambitions to learn the target language.

This study provided in-depth understanding about motivational strategies preferred by JFL teachers and students and how does differ the perception related to using strategies. Therefore, this study suggests a number of implications for teachers in terms of Japanese language teaching. First of all the findings can be applied to improve teaching practice in foreign language education in Sri Lanka by providing facilities to improve the teachers' knowledge and skills to use strategies effectively for enhancing students' motivation. Therefore, it would be worthwhile if teachers try out these strategies or at least most of them in their classroom while considering that learners are different and thus different strategies affect differently with various type of students. Hence, teachers should be aware of their teaching methodology and behaviors in the classroom since teacher is the most important role in the classroom.

Further findings will be supported to relevant authorities to organize teacher training programmes in order to introduce teaching methodology which support to enhance student's motivation. Moreover, it can be recommended that future research should investigate the actual use of motivational strategies in a language classroom to identify the most suitable strategies for Sri Lankan students in order to improve their level of motivation as suggested in previous studies for better understanding in this area. Further, it will be worthwhile to find out how students and teachers demographic information and other factors affect the relationship between students' motivation and motivational strategies.

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